

A Risk Score Model to Support Early Identification and Prevention of Type 2 Diabetes Incorporating Social Determinants of Health

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Abstract

Aims: To develop a clinically relevant risk score model for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) by integrating conventional risk factors with social determinants of health (SDOH) using population-level data from the CDC 2015 Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS).

Methods: Random Forest, Support vector machines (SVM), Logistic Regression, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost were applied to the cleaned and curated CDC 2015 BRFSS dataset. The dataset was divided into a training dataset (n=2700) and a testing dataset (n=300). 10-fold cross-validation on all algorithms and clustering using K-means algorithm were conducted for data analysis. Logistic regression was used to generate the risk score for each factor.

Results: The study identified positive and negative predictors of T2DM. The significant positive predictors included well-established clinical factors like BMI, Age, and sex. Emerging risk factors for T2DM, referred to as social determinants of health (SDOH), were also found to be significant in this study. For instance, higher income and improved access to healthcare were associated with lower predicted risk.

Conclusion: These findings support targeted screening and preventive interventions for populations at elevated risk of Type 2 Diabetes. The logistic regression-based risk score model has great predictive power and is unique in that it utilizes underrepresented features with promising potential like the SDOH along with conventional clinical risk factors. The risk score relevance in public health initiatives to halt diabetes is based on its use of a diverse survey population that simulates real-world scenarios. The risk score model thus has great real-world applicability and is appropriate for public health initiatives.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Risk Prediction, Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) and Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a disease caused by complete or partial deficiency of insulin secretion by the pancreas that results in long-term hyperglycemia and abnormalities in lipid, protein, and carbohydrate metabolism in the body.¹ The number of people with Diabetes in America is poised to increase by 165% from 11 million in

2000 to 29 million in 2050. The burden of Diabetes is borne by society through higher direct medical costs for doctor visits and medications, loss in productivity, premature mortality, and reduced quality of life. The cost of economic burden in 2017 was \$327 billion and in 2022 was \$412.9 billion.² People suffering from Type 2 Diabetes mellitus (T2DM) also suffer from many comorbidities like cardiovascular diseases, diabetic nephropathy, diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy, lower limb amputations, and other conditions. There is a 1.3 to 2 times greater risk associated with premature mortality in Diabetic patients as compared to normal people and this is primarily due to cardiovascular disease related to Diabetes.^{3,4} It is a globally agreed target to stop the increase in the number of cases of Diabetes by 2025.⁵

Studies have shown that simple changes in diet and physical activity can reduce the occurrence of T2DM in people with impaired glucose regulation by $> 50\%$ ⁶. Lifestyle-related risk factors associated with Type 2 Diabetes are age, ethnic background, obesity, genetics, and family history.⁷ Additional risk factors that can also contribute to Diabetes risk are stress, poor sleep habits, and sleep disorders.^{8,9} Factors like job opportunities, income, education, and neighborhoods belong to domains of conditions collectively termed as social determinants of health (SDOH)¹⁰ and also contribute to disease risk. A detailed list has been given in Table S1.¹¹⁻¹⁴

According to many studies, T2DM can be prevented through relevant lifestyle adjustments. These lifestyle changes primarily consist of weight loss through the consumption of a currently recommended diet consisting of healthy fat, and fiber, and an increased intake of whole grains, fruits, and vegetables along with increased physical activity. Prevention can only be efficient when strategies are in place to detect at-risk populations for T2DM that will benefit from medical interventions and tailored treatments. Diabetes risk categorization, combined with screening for individuals at-risk, can be done with multi-factorial risk prediction models.^{15,16} Building on traditional risk scores, the risk score designed in this study is novel for a few reasons and offers a new dimension to predictive accuracy. Although the association between T2DM and SDOH is well-researched, the use of these factors clinically is very limited. Using advanced machine learning approaches and R programming language, the study models the complex interplay between lifestyle, SDOH, and disease risk and provides a sophisticated data-driven tool for prevention, management, and mitigation of the disease. This novel approach addresses a critical missing component in clinical risk scores by implementing SDOH insights into actionable risk predictions.¹⁷ A similar study akin to this paper was done by Xie et al¹⁸ but the work done here differs in that it uses a different dataset, 22 risk factors as opposed to the 27 factors they had used, in the predictive models used for data analysis, incorporating a 10-fold cross-validation on all the machine learning algorithms, and clustering analysis using the K-means algorithm to generate a reliable and robust model. Abbas et al¹⁹ used the same methodology for their Diabetes risk score but used the Qatar Biobank dataset and a different set of risk factors.

2 Methods

2.1 2015 CDC BRFSS survey Dataset

The publicly available 2015 CDC Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance Survey (BRFSS) dataset with 444,1457 individual answers to 330 factors is available from the Kaggle database and the link is given here-<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/alexteboul/diabetes-health-indicators-dataset>. The dataset was streamlined to include 253,680 survey participants responses with 22 significant factors. The outcome variable was Diabetes_012 and was encoded as 0 for no disease and 1 for patients with either prediabetes or Diabetes20 in the Kaggle dataset. This streamlined Kaggle dataset was used in this study. R studio desktop version 4.3.2 was installed and used for Data analysis. The dataset was cleaned and preprocessed by handling missing values, null values, and outliers. The entire list of factors with a brief description of the variable is given in Table S2.

2.2 Training, testing, and validation dataset

This modified Kaggle dataset was condensed and only a portion of the original dataset (n=3000) was taken for efficient processing as the original dataset was large and had 253,680 observations. The condensed dataset had to be balanced as research mentions this as a solution for getting around the issues of class imbalance which was encountered in the ML algorithms.²¹ The condensed datasets contained an equal number of negative and positive outcomes. Model validation was done by splitting the balanced dataset into 2 distinct subsets, with a 90:10 split for the training and test datasets, respectively. Another subset from the original cleaned Kaggle dataset was kept for validation (n=2000) as the validation dataset. This validation dataset was used for K-means clustering analysis and predictive performance of the model.²² Subsequently, the risk score model was tested on the original Kaggle dataset to assess the model's robustness. The methodology adopted to generate the predictive model is shown in Figure 1.

2.3 Logistic Regression and Machine Learning models

Multivariate logistic regression and four other machine learning algorithms which are Random Forest, XGBoost, Gradient Boosting, and Support vector machine were used for Data analysis. Advanced model validation was performed using 10-fold cross- validation on all these models. The metrics that were calculated comprised of Balanced accuracy (BACC), Accuracy (ACC), specificity, sensitivity, and Area under the curve (AUC).The use of ML algorithms, 10-fold cross-validation, and the metrics uses the same methodology outlined by Abbas et al.¹⁹ Logistic regression was used as the primary algorithm as it is a widely used statistical model typically used in multivariate analysis for modeling a binary dependant variable like the outcome in this dataset.²³

The diagnostic model yielded β coefficients and odds ratio for each predictor variable. These coefficients provide a mathematical representation of the contribution of each predictor for the risk of the outcome.²⁴ For the sake of simplicity and for scaling, the risk score was obtained by multiplying the β coefficient by 10, and by rounding to the nearest integer. Results were reported as means and standard deviation for quantitative variables, and as percentage for Binary variables and categorical variables, along with p values and standard errors.

2.4 Risk scores for predicting health outcomes

Binary variables like HighChol have fixed values, BMI being numeric can vary widely, and Age being ordinal categorical has higher scores for higher categories. For simplicity, only the baseline risk score is given but categories were expanded while calculating the cumulative risk scores.

2.5 Evaluating Model Performance with Youden's J statistic and K-means algorithm

To reduce errors due to false negatives and false positives and to report only true negatives and true positives,^{25,26} a modified Youden's J statistic or a weighted version of Youden's J statistic was used to improve specificity and sensitivity scores.²⁷ The optimal cut-off point was chosen to prioritize sensitivity as Diabetes is highly prevalent, and missing a positive case poses a greater risk than a false positive. A weight of 2/3rds of sensitivity was assigned for specificity for this purpose.

Threshold risk scores and metrics for each risk score including the cut-off risk score established by the modified Youden's J statistic were gauged for the model. These methodologies were adapted from the study by Abbas et al.¹⁹ A K-means algorithm was used to create clusters for the validation and training dataset, for data analysis, which resulted in 3 clusters each.

3 Results

3.1 Dataset Overview: Discovering Important Insights

The training and testing datasets were analyzed for their baseline characteristics which are given in Table 1. Age, High BP, HighChol, and BMI, which are established risk factors for Diabetes, were analyzed for their correlation with T2DM outcomes as done by Abbas et al.¹⁹ The results across the entire Kaggle dataset for the disease correlation with risk factors are presented in Table S3.

3.2 Risk scores for predicting health outcomes

The risk score along with β coefficients, standard errors, odds ratio, and P-value is given in table S4. In the risk prediction, the significant positive predictors for Diabetes were Age, BMI, CholCheck with a risk score of 17, HighBP with 7 points, HighChol with 7 points, and General health with a score of 6.

3.3 Risk categorization into risk groups in the datasets

The cumulative risk scores were calculated for each observation in the training and test dataset, and based on their interquartile range (IQR), risk categories were created. Research studies use IQR for outlier detection, but in this study, this statistical method was used to get threshold scores from the cumulative risk scores, for creating 3 risk categories: low risk, medium risk and high risk. The IQR is essentially the difference between the upper quartile (Q3) and the lower quartile (Q1) and shows the range in which the middle 50% of the data lies. The risk percentages across training and test datasets are shown in Table S5. There is consistency across the testing and training datasets; as the risk category increases from low to high the percentage of patients with T2DM/Prediabetes also increases.

Table 1 Baseline characteristics of training and testing dataset

	Training dataset		Test Dataset	
	Controls	Case	Controls	Case
HighChol	36	67.04	33.33	68.67
HighBP	36.4	75.03	26	80
CholCheck	96	99.55	96.66	99.33
Fruits	65.48	59.85	69.33	54.66
Veggies	82.96	75.03	86	78.66
Stroke	2.81	10.29	2.66	9.33
HeartDiseaseorAttack	7.48	21.92	6.66	22
DiffWalk	12.51	36.29	15.33	38
HvyAlcoholConsump	6.81	2.29	6	2.66
PhysActivity	77.4	63.85	75.33	58.66
Smoker	43.11	50.37	42.66	49.33
AnyHealthcare	95.18	94.59	92.66	94
NoDocbcCost	7.33	11.25	9.33	10
Sex (% Men)	47.28	52.72	52.5	47.5
BMI	27.78 ± 5.77	32.04 ± 7.22	27.45 ± 5.77	32.35 ± 10.17
Age	56.04 ± 15.89	63.46 ± 11.83	55.32 ± 16.98	64.88 ± 11.93
Education	5.12 ± 0.94	4.74 ± 1.09	5.08 ± 0.98	4.63 ± 1.01
General health	2.37 ± 1.02	3.29 ± 1.02	2.47 ± 1.05	3.23 ± 0.99
Mental Health	2.87 ± 6.78	4.79 ± 9.25	3.04 ± 6.81	4.97 ± 9.53
Physical health	3.89 ± 8.36	8 ± 11.42	4.05 ± 8.47	7.37 ± 10.99
Income	6.33 ± 1.96	5.17 ± 2.22	5.95 ± 2.07	5.24 ± 2.13

Table values are percentages for binary variables (For all 1, for instance HighChol=1 implying patients having high cholesterol) and mean and standard deviation for continuous variables. P-values were calculated using one way ANOVA test and all p-values were found significant $p < 0.001$. Control is Diabetes_012=0 or no disease and case is Diabetes_012=1 or with Disease.

3.4 Baseline Characteristics

The baseline characteristics between the test and training dataset are shown in Table 1. About the participants, in the training dataset, 36% with high cholesterol (HighChol=1) were controls (no disease) and almost twice the number were cases (with disease) at 67.04%. Men (Sex=1) were higher in both cases (50.29 %) and in controls (45.11%) in the training dataset. The same trend was observed in the test dataset, with HighChol at 33.3% for controls and 68.67% for cases. Men (Sex=1) were 52.5% in control, and 47.5% in cases in the test set. CholCheck was also comparable between control (96% in training and 96.66% in test) and cases (99.5% in training and 99.3% in test) across datasets, HighBP was almost twice the amount in cases (75.03%) as in control (36.4%) in the training dataset, and in the test dataset the same trend was observed with cases (80%) and controls (26%). In Table 2, the baseline characteristics of training and test datasets across risk groups and variables are shown. Variables associated with a higher risk of developing T2DM are at a higher percentage in the high-risk group like HighChol, HighBP, BMI, and General health.

3.5 Evaluation metrics of all the models

The random forest model had an AUC of 84% with specificity and sensitivity of 70.7% and 79.3% respectively and Balanced accuracy (BACC) at 75%. Xg Boost had an AUC of 80% with sensitivity at 70%, specificity at 76.7%, and Balanced accuracy at 73.3%. The Gradient boosting model had an AUC of 84.3% with a specificity of 73.3%, sensitivity of 80.7%, and BACC of 77%. The SVM model had an AUC of 81.5%, specificity of 72%, sensitivity of 76%, and Balanced accuracy was 74%. The logistic regression model had an AUC of 84.74% for the test dataset with specificity at 75.61%, sensitivity at 72.62%, and BACC at 74.12%. The logistic regression model on the entire dataset yielded an AUC of 81.58%, specificity of 75.61%, sensitivity of 72.62%, and BACC of 74.12%. The logistic regression model was run on the balanced training dataset and it generated an AUC of 83.24%, with a 95% CI ranging from 81.72% to 83.24%. The BACC was 76%, specificity was 77.5%, and sensitivity was 74.4%. The test dataset had an AUC of 84.74%, with a 95% CI ranging from 80.4% to 89%. The Specificity was 77.33%, sensitivity was 73.33%, and BACC was 75.33%. The evaluation metrics for all models are shown in Fig S1. The AUC for the logistic regression model is shown in Fig 2.

3.6 Clustering analysis using the K-means clustering algorithm

A K-means algorithm was used to create clusters for the validation and training dataset, which resulted in 3 clusters each. The baseline characteristics of the validation and training dataset for selected features are displayed in Table 3. In the cluster distribution, the training and validation datasets showed similar trends. Cluster 1 had a high percentage of individuals with HighBP (66.4% in the training dataset and 62.7% in the validation dataset), HighChol (99.6% in the training dataset and 99.1% in the validation dataset), and PhysActivity (70.52% in the training dataset and 69.08% in the validation dataset). Cluster 2 had a higher

percentage of individuals with PhysActivity (83.6% in training and 83.7% in validation). Cluster 3 had a high number of participants with HeartDiseaseorAttack, HighBP, HighChol, and a lower number with PhysActivity.

3.7 Evaluating Model Performance with Youden's J statistic

For a cut-off point of 67 established by a modified Youden's J statistic for the training dataset here are the metrics with their 95% Confidence intervals in parentheses: specificity 46.81% (44.16%-49.48%), sensitivity 95.7% (94.48%-96.66%), BACC 72.72% (68.84%-77.21%), accuracy (ACC) 71.23% (69.48%-73%), positive predictive value (PPV) 64.27% (62.15%-66.34%), and negative predictive value (NPV) 91.59% (89.28%-93.44%) with an AUC value of 0.83(0.81-0.84). In the test dataset, the metrics were: specificity 48% (40.15%-55.94%), sensitivity 97.33% (93.34%-98.95%), BACC 72.66% (68.71%-76.97%), accuracy (ACC) 56.28% (51%- 61.66%), positive predictive value (PPV) 65.17% (58.73%-71.11%), negative predictive value (NPV) of 94.73% (87.23%-97.93%), and an AUC value of 0.84(0.800-0.89). The different metrics at various thresholds of cumulative risk score are given in Table 4 for the training dataset and in Table 5 for the test dataset.

The different metrics at various thresholds of cumulative risk score are given in Table 3 for the training dataset and in Table 4 for the test dataset.

Figure 1: Steps for Generating the Risk Prediction Model

Steps involved were 1) **Data collection:** Gather information from survey 2) **Data Preprocessing:** Clean and prepare data 3) **Feature selection:** Select the variables 4) **Balanced dataset creation** with 50:50 ratio of outcome 5) **Dataset splitting** 6) **Validation set creation:** n=2000 from original dataset 7) **Model training:**

With 5 Machine learning models 8) **Creating risk prediction model** using the selected Logistic regression model

4 Discussion

4.1 Statistical and Data analysis

The small standard errors (SE) and $p < 0.05$ suggest reliable β coefficient estimates and statistical significance. This indicates that the model prediction is highly accurate and can be used to derive meaningful insights. Factors with $p > 0.05$ were Smoker, NoDocbcCost, Sex, and Education. The higher p-values can still be helpful in a clinical scenario where small effects are important. This means that these four variables might have practical significance, especially in healthcare settings, although they lack statistical significance.²⁸ In the risk score, there are positive predictors like High blood pressure and High Cholesterol that contribute to risk and negative predictors of risk that reduce the risk of the outcome like Physical activity, and fruits that are consistent with our current knowledge on what causes Type II Diabetes and helps with prevention of T2DM.^{29,30} Overall, this study demonstrates extremely good performance metrics with an AUC of 83.24% on its training dataset and an AUC of 84.74% on the test dataset and shows good discriminatory power to differentiate between risk categories.^{31,32}

Figure 2: Area under curve (AUC) for the logistic regression model

4.2 Clustering analysis

Clustering analysis revealed that cluster 3 is the unhealthiest with a higher number of cases with HighBP, HeartDiseaseorAttack, and higher instances of participants with poor GenHlth combined with low instances of beneficial behaviors like PhysActivity. Cluster 3 is the detrimental group and should be targeted first with tailored interventions to improve these factors and reduce risk. The same trend is seen across validation and

training datasets indicating consistency across datasets. Cluster 2 is the healthiest with lower instances of positive risk factors like HighBP, HeartDiseaseorAttack and GenHlth. In Table 3, some factors were found to be not significant ($p > 0.05$), which are HeavyAlcoholConsumption and Sex in instances that are men. This could be due to a lack of variation in the dataset; the dataset could benefit from adding more factors like family history of diabetes, and type of diet. The risk stratification is similar across clusters between validation and training datasets with cluster 1 entirely composed of medium- risk individuals, cluster 2 having a significant portion of participants in the low-risk and majority in medium-risk group, and cluster 3 having the highest percentage of high-risk individuals indicating that this is the population of individuals with severe health risk factors.

Table 2 The risk percentage across different groups in training and test dataset

Variable	Low Risk	Medium Risk	High Risk	Low Risk	Medium Risk	High Risk
Training Dataset	Test Dataset					
HighChol	12(5.06)	1251(53.87)	128(90.78)	1(4.34)	140(53.84)	12(70.58)
CholCheck	202(85.3)	2297(98.92)	17(100)	19(82.6)	258(99.23)	17(100)
HighChol	12(5.06)	1251(53.87)	128(90.78)	1(4.34)	140(53.84)	12(70.58)
Heartdiseaseorattack	0	339(14.59)	58(41.13)	0	37(14.23)	6(35.29)
PhysActivity	208(87.76)	1640(70.62)	59(41.84)	20(86.95)	174(66.92)	7(41.17)
Sex	88(37.13)	1133(48.79)	67(47.51)	8(34.78)	109(41.92)	3(17.64)
HvyAlcoholConsump*	35(14.76)	88(3.78)	0	3(13.04)	10(3.84)	0
Sex=Male***	88(37.1)	1133(48.8)	67(47.5)	8(34.8)	109(41.9)	3(17.6)
Sex=Femal	149(62.9)	1189(51.2)	74(52.5)	15(65.2)	151(58.1)	14(82.4)
BMI	23.78±3.1	29.8±6.01	41.83±9.4	24.13±3.8	29.03±6.2	50.94±19.9
GenHlth	1.57±0.64	2.85±1.03	4.48±0.	1.6±0.58	2.87±1.02	4.11±0.85

P < 0.001 ** and ***p > 0.05

4.3 Risk Scores usefulness

A risk score is needed to predict disease and offer preventive interventions through medications and lifestyle changes. The 2015 BRFSS based risk score in this study uses 22 factors together with advanced machine learning models with 10-fold cross-validation, and clustering analysis and has good metrics all pointing to a robust predictive model for T2DM or prediabetes. A study conducted by Xie et al as a follow-up of a Finnish Diabetes prevention study has reported a reduction in the risk for Diabetes incidence using lifestyle interventions like increased physical activity, and changing diet that included increasing intake of dietary fibers.³³ A study conducted by the China Kadoorie Biobank collaborative group found that the incidence of

early-onset coronary artery disease, ischemic stroke, and late-onset CAD was reduced by 14.7, 2.7, and 2.6 folds respectively by employing favorable lifestyle choices.³⁴ Such is the power of risk scores, but it remains disheartening that its power has not been harnessed in metabolic disease scenarios; there are a lot of risk scores and models for Diabetes but none have been used or practiced by clinicians.³⁵

Table 3 Baseline Characteristics of features in training and validation datasets after clustering using K-means algorithm along with Risk stratification

Variable	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Training			
HighBP	804(66.4%)	232(22.9%)	355(74.11%)
HighChol	1206(99.6%)	956(94.6%)	478(99.79%)
PhysActivity	854(70.52%)	840(83.16%)	213(44.46%)
HeartDiseaseorAttack	230(18.99%)	22(2.17%)	145(30.27%)
HeavyAlcoholConsumption	22(1.81%)	90(8.91%)	11(2.29%)
Sex (% Men)	652(53.83%)	436(43.16%)	200(41.7%)
Sex (% women)	559(46.16%)	574(56.83%)	279(58.25%)
GenHlth	2.99±0.817	1.99±0.796	4.17±0.837
BMI**	31.4±6.19	26.2±4.18	34±9.02
Low Risk	0	1195(98.67)	16(1.32%)
Medium risk	237(23.44%)	773(76.45%)	0
High Risk	0	354(73.90%)	125(26.09%)
Validation			
HighBP	467(62.7%)	252(24.16%)	144(67.6%)
HighChol	738(99.19%)	973(93.3%)	211(99.1%)
PhysActivity	514(69.08%)	873(83.70%)	92(43.19%)
HeartDiseaseorAttack	125(16.8%)	18(1.73%)	56(26.29%)
HeavyAlcoholConsumption	12(1.61%)	87(8.34%)	4(1.87%)
Sex (% Men)	358(48.11%)	474(45.44%)	70(32.86%)
Sex (% women)	386(51.88%)	569(54.55%)	143(67.13%)
GenHlth*	2.99±0.81	1.99±0.79	4.16±0.83
BMI	30.73±6.49	25.65±4.25	33.28±10.59
Low Risk	0	736(98.92%)	8(1.07%)
Medium Risk	277(26.55%)	766(73.44%)	0
High Risk	0	171(80.28%)	42(19.71%)

p<0.001 for all the variables * p<0.05, **p=0.5

4.4 The positive risk factors for T2DM

Features like HighBP, HighChol, and BMI have been identified as significant predictors of the development of T2DM in various other studies.⁷In this study, the positive predictors of risk are CholCheck, HighBP, HighChol, Stroke, Age, BMI, DiffWalk, GenHlth, and HeartDiseaseorAttack. High blood pressure has been shown to raise the risk of diabetes by 60% than in those with normal blood pressure.³⁶ Scientific evidence from the ARIC study (Atherosclerosis risk in communities), CARDIA study (Coronary Artery Risk development in young adults), and the Framingham Heart study offspring cohort, altogether with a Size of

10,893 participants revealed hypertension as a key risk factor, typically observed before the onset of Diabetes.³⁷

A person with dyslipidemia or high cholesterol will test for A1c in the prediabetes range of 4.8-5.6% due to the association between insulin resistance and high cholesterol in the blood.³⁸ Triglycerides (TG), total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein (HDL-c), and low-density lipoprotein (LDL-c) are linked to the development of Prediabetes and T2DM; elevated levels of cholesterol lead to β cell dysfunction that causes impaired insulin secretion.³⁹ CholCheck variable with a risk score of 17 indicates that individuals who have had a cholesterol check are more likely engaged in bettering their health. This behavior can lead to earlier detection of risk factors associated with T2DM. In predictive health models, the absence of regular health checkups such as cholesterol tests is a sturdy indicator of a higher risk due to lack of preventive care.

Diabetes risk increases from 7% to 70% in men (above 18 years) and 12% to 74 % in women when BMI increases from 18.5 kg/m to more than 35kg/m.⁴⁰ Sex was a risk factor in this study with men more predisposed to the disease. Age with a risk score of 2 significantly impacts risk. This is because with age senescent β cells in the pancreas increase. This results in defective insulin secretion, resulting in abnormal glucose metabolism that leads to T2DM.⁴¹ DiffWalk can be a consequence as well as a risk factor. Diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN), a common complication of T2DM can diminish a person's ability to walk with peripheral nerve degeneration and defective nerve regeneration.⁴² With walking or physical mobility becoming difficult, one is forced into a sedentary lifestyle that can augment the risk of diabetes through insulin resistance.⁴³

4.5 The negative players

The negative predictors were physical activity, heavy alcohol consumption, healthcare, income, fruits, and education. Interestingly, heavy alcohol consumption was one of the negative risk predictors which is not surprising as scientific evidence points to a beneficial side to moderate alcohol consumption, a paradox. Research points to a phenomenon where minimal drinking of alcohol, and chronic exposure to alcohol improves insulin sensitivity leading to a reduced risk of T2DM.⁴⁴ Moderate drinking is beneficial in reducing Type II Diabetes risk which is what is seen in the work done in this paper. There is a rationale for why this column in the CDC dataset should have been labeled moderate drinking as opposed to HvyAlcoholConsump and this is discussed in the supplementary section.

Having healthcare access means there can be more preventive care and timely treatment for mitigating diabetes risk. Higher income allows for more quality in medical care, food, and the neighborhood a person lives in promoting better health and reduced health risks. Smoker, as with the variable CholCheck, could be receiving a risk score of -1 as smokers who regularly monitor their health are more likely to adopt healthier habits and be more vigilant in maintaining a good health status. This could partially offset the risks associated with smoking. Additionally, the observed risk score might be due to an interaction effect of this factor with another variable.⁴⁵

4.6 Dataset importance

Choosing this dataset and features, as explained earlier, was based on well-established literature on risk factors. This includes the biological risk factors like age, high cholesterol, and BMI and SDOH's like Income, and healthcare. The 2015 CDC BRFSS dataset was chosen in particular, because it is more representative of the prevalence of Diabetes among a broad range of

Table 4 Threshold risk scores and the performance metrics associated with it in the training dataset

TRS	Specificity % (95% CI)	Sensitivity % (95% CI)	BACC % (95% CI)	ACC % (95% CI)	PPV % (95% CI)	NPV % (95% CI)	AUC % (95% CI)
40	2.66 (1.87-3.67)	99.92 (99.58-99.98)	51.30 (50.89-51.74)	51.31 (49.51-53.18)	50.65 (48.73-2.57)	97.29 (85.83-99.93)	0.83 (0.81-0.84)
45	6.44 (5.19-7.88)	99.85 (99.46-99.98)	53.12 (52.49-53.76)	53.16 (51.25-55.03)	51.62 (49.69-3.56)	97.75 (92.11-99.72)	
50	12.96 (11.21-14.87)	99.77 (99.35-99.95)	56.37 (55.53-57.27)	56.37 (54.55-58.29)	53.41 (51.44-55.37)	98.31 (95.15-99.65)	
60	30.51 (28.06-33.05)	98.44 (97.63-99.03)	64.49 (63.22-65.72)	64.47 (62.62-66.37)	58.62 (56.56-60.66)	95.15 (92.68-96.97)	
67	46.81 (44.16-49.48)	95.7 (94.48-96.66)	72.72 (68.84-77.21)	71.23 (69.48-73)	64.27 (62.15-66.34)	91.59 (89.28-93.44)	
70	52.88 (50.18-55.57)	93.18 (91.70-94.47)	73.05 (71.54-74.53)	72.99 (71.40-74.63)	66.42 (64.24-68.54)	88.58 (86.18-90.69)	
80	74.96 (72.56-77.25)	77.33 (75-79.54)	76.12 (74.58-77.69)	76.16 (74.55-77.62)	75.54 (73.18-77.78)	76.78 (74.40-79.03)	
90	88.29 (86.46-89.96)	49.85 (47.15-52.55)	69.01 (67.48-70.51)	69.05 (67.48-70.88)	80.98 (78.15-83.6)	63.77 (61.55-65.96)	
100	96 (94.81-96.98)	23.33 (21.10-25.68)	59.64 (58.47-60.85)	59.67 (57.74-61.55)	85.36 (81.34-88.81)	55.59 (53.55-57.62)	
105	98.59 (97.81-99.15)	13.77 (11.98-15.73)	56.16 (55.25-57.08)	56.14 (54.29-57.96)	90.73 (85.9-94.32)	53.34 (51.36-55.31)	
110	99.48 (98.93-99.79)	7.44 (6.06-8.93)	53.45 (52.74-54.21)	53.42 (51.70-55.25)	93.45 (86.98-97.32)	51.79 (49.84-53.73)	
120	99.92 (99.58-99.99)	1.62 (1.02-2.45)	50.76 (50.44-51.15)	50.77 (48.96-52.66)	95.65 (78.05-99.89)	50.39 (48.48-52.30)	
130	100 (99.72-100)	0.29 (0.08-0.75)	50.15	50.13	100	50.07	

			(50.03-50.31)	(48.25-52)	(39.76-100)	(48-16-51.97)
136	100 (99.72-100)	0.07 (0-0.41)	50.05 (50.03-50.14)	49.98 (48.14-51.92)	100 (2.5-100)	50.01 (48.11-51.92)

BACC is balanced accuracy, ACC is accuracy, PPV is positive predictive value, NPV is negative predictive value, AUC is area under the curve. Threshold Risk scores have been abbreviated as TRS.

Table 5 Threshold risk scores and the performance metrics associated with it in the test dataset

TRS	Specificity % (95% CI)	Sensitivity % (95% CI)	BACC % (95% CI)	ACC % (95% CI)	PPV % (95% CI)	NPV % (95% CI)	AUC % (95% CI)
40	2 (0.4-5.7)	100 (97.57-100)	51.06 (50.32-52.24)	50.89 (45.33-56.33)	50.50 (44.67-56.32)	100 (43.85-100)	0.84 (0.80-.89)
45	7.22 (3.71-12.74)	100 (97.57-100)	53.66 (51.76-55.88)	53.6 (48.33-59)	51.90 (45.97-57.79)	100 (74.11-100)	
50	11.33 (6.74-17.52)	100 (97.57-100)	55.68 (53.28-58.15)	55.54 (50.33-61.66)	53 (47-58.93)	100 (81.56-100)	
60	33.33 (25.85-41.48)	100 (97.57-100)	66.68 (62.9-70.56)	66.67 (61.33-71.66)	60 (53.68-66.12)	100 (92.88-100)	
67	48 (40.15-55.94)	97.33 (93.34-98.95)	72.66 (68.71-76.97)	56.28 (51-61.66)	65.17 (58.73-71.11)	94.73 (87.23-97.93)	
70	54.66 (46.34-62.8)	92 (86.44-95.79)	73.28 (68.99-77.76)	73.36 (68.66-78.33)	66.99 (60.11-73.36)	87.23 (78.76-93.22)	
80	74 (66.21-80.81)	76.66 (69.07-83.17)	75.38 (70.54-80.5)	75.38 (70.66-80)	74.67 (67.04-81.33)	76.02 (68.26-82.69)	
90	88.66 (82.47-93.25)	47.33 (39.13-55.64)	68.08 (63.16-72.74)	68.01 (62.66-73.33)	80.68 (70.88-88.32)	62.73 (55.84-69.26)	
100	97.33 (93.31-99.26)	24.66 (18-32.36)	61.01 (57.5-64.67)	61.06 (55.66-66)	90.24 (76.86-97.27)	56.37 (50.09-62.49)	
105	98 (94.26-99.58)	14.66 (9.42-21.35)	72.66 (68.71-76.97)	56.49 (51-61.67)	88 (68.78-97.45)	53.45 (47.36-59.46)	
110	98.66 (95.26-99.83)	7.33 (3.71-12.74)	52.94 (50.68-55.41)	52.97 (46.66-58.33)	84.61 (54.55-98.07)	51.56 (45.62-57.48)	
120	99.33 (96.34-99.98)	2.66 (0.73-6.68)	51.04 (49.67-52.46)	50.99 (45.66-56.66)	80 (28.35-99.49)	50.50 (44.65-56.35)	
130	99.33	2	50.69	50.7	75	50.33	

	(96.34-99.98)	(0.41-5.73)	(49.45-52.03)	(45.33-56)	(19.41-99.36)	(44.49-56.17)
136	99.33	1.33	50.36	50.4	66.66	50.16
	(96.34-99.98)	(0.16-4.73)	(49.26-51.5)	(44.66-56)	(9.42-99.15)	(44.33-55.99)

Demographic groups, as it is a centrally designed national-telephonic survey. Many research studies focus on specific ethnic groups, for instance, Pima Indians, but this survey dataset is more inclusive and more comprehensive of the diverse US population thereby providing an extremely valuable resource for public health research. Finally, the survey data is very credible, as numerous research studies have confirmed their accuracy and reliability.

The Kaggle dataset derived from the CDC's BRFSS dataset covers relevant socio-demographic and behavioral variables making it a reliable predictive health model for diverse populations. By incorporating relevant health-based risk behaviors, chronic conditions, relatable social determinants, and an inclusive representation of the US population, this dataset supports accurate identification of risk factors thereby paving the way for effective interventions for diseases like T2DM and Prediabetes. This model is poised to become a robust model for public health initiatives in T2DM prevention and mitigation.

4.7 Future directions

A more composite risk score model with additional features that include the Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) like employment, neighborhood, and cultural beliefs, and using the original CDC dataset with its additional columns like race, diet, and sleeping habits in a subsequent paper could be the next step. Additionally, incorporating genetic data in the risk score model could make the model more reliable. Experimenting with different percentages of training, testing, and validation datasets can be also carried out, as studies have shown that this approach helps with improving risk scores during data analysis.⁴⁶

Additionally, the current outcome combines Prediabetes and T2DM. Future studies can be planned to separate these outcomes and determine risks specifically for prediabetes or T2DM. This will help identify the risk factors associated with a prediabetes progression to T2DM disease status. Identification of these risk factors can also pave the way for interventions to revert prediabetes to normal health. Prediabetes takes about 5 years to progress to T2DM, and is a midway state between normal glucose levels and high blood glucose levels that is characterized as T2DM. With diet modification and physical exercise, it is possible to revert prediabetes to normal blood glucose levels and prevent the onset of Diabetes.⁴⁷

5 Conclusion

A risk score health model was generated using the 2015 CDC BRFSS dataset to diagnose T2DM or prediabetes outcomes. This was developed using R programming language and 5 machine learning models. The risk factors used in this study are both conventional and non-standard. The study is extremely insightful in that in addition to traditional risk factors, atypical factors also seem to play a major role in T2DM risk.

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Data Availability Statement: Ethics approval was not required for this study as it used publicly available, anonymized data from the Kaggle repository (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/alexteboul/diabetes-health-indicators-dataset>).

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